

Measuring Efficiency of Regional Healthcare: Application of the DEA Approach

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Abstract

Purpose of the study: Comparative analysis of the efficiency of regional healthcare systems in the Russian Federation.

Research methods: The research is based on a two-stage Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). First, efficiency is estimated using DEA models. Then, a Tobit regression is used to identify exogenous (environmental) factors that significantly impact efficiency levels. Two DEA models were applied: an output-oriented model and an input-oriented model, both with variable returns to scale. The results were then compared.

Results. Eighteen regions of the Russian Federation were found to be efficient according to both DEA models, while 67 others were identified as inefficient. The rank, as well as the set of reference decision-making units (DMUs) for the inefficient DMUs, depend largely on the model chosen. According to both models, the healthcare system of the Chukotka Autonomous Okrug demonstrates the lowest efficiency of all. Regression analysis revealed that lifestyle factors significantly impact the efficiency of regional healthcare systems. This highlights the importance of efforts to encourage a culture of self-preservation behaviour in Russian society.

Conclusion. The DEA approach used in this study has several advantages. It enables estimating the technical efficiency of DMUs, along with producing a set of reference DMUs and quantitative estimates of input and output slacks. This makes it particularly well-suited for estimating healthcare efficiency. For this approach to be adopted more widely, however, the choice of inputs, outputs and model specification must be rigorously justified.

Keywords

efficient frontier, DEA, healthcare, regions, technical efficiency, Tobit model

JEL codes: I18, C67

Introduction

In response to an urgent need for more efficient healthcare systems worldwide, the global research community has produced a significant body of theoretical, methodological and empirical work examining the efficiency of healthcare systems and their components, including services and facilities.

The concept of efficiency was initially developed within economic theory, where it is divided into two categories: productive efficiency and allocative efficiency. Productive efficiency is achieved by obtaining maximum output or minimum resource consumption. Allocative efficiency, in turn, is achieved by obtaining a set of outcomes that maximises social welfare. Within productive efficiency, various authors, not fully aligned with each other, distinguish several subtypes, including technical, price, allocative, and scale efficiency. Technical efficiency is defined as achieving the maximum possible output with a fixed amount of resources or achieving the desired output with the minimum possible resources. Price efficiency is about getting the most value for a given amount of resources used or using a combination of resources that achieves a given outcome at the lowest possible cost. Scale efficiency is achieved by choosing the optimal output. Allocative efficiency is achieved by using the set of resources that maximises the value of the output. All these definitions of efficiency are applicable to healthcare facilities. A good systematic review of research in this field in terms of these definitions can be found in (Lötscher-Stamm and Lenzin 2024).

In his seminal work (Farrell 1957), the author developed a theory of productive efficiency based on the concept of the efficient frontier, proposing a methodological approach to measuring it. Recognising the difficulty of obtaining efficient frontiers for complex processes and systems through theoretical calculations, the author proposed using the best observable examples to construct them. Farrell's work has inspired many researchers whose efforts have shaped the main approaches to be found in current literature on healthcare efficiency estimation. DEA (Data Envelopment Analysis) and SFA (Stochastic Frontier Analysis) are the most widespread of these. A systematic review of 317 studies on healthcare facility efficiency estimation was conducted in (Hollingsworth 2008). According to this review, 48% of studies used DEA, 19% used DEA in combination with regression analysis, and 18% used SFA. The same study found that efficiency analysis had been applied to a variety of healthcare assets, including hospitals, doctors, programmes, services and national healthcare systems, with hospitals being the most frequent asset to estimate (51%). However, there has been growing interest in the comparative analysis of the efficiency of national healthcare systems since the 2000s. This came to the fore following a report by the World Health Organisation which estimated the efficiency of national healthcare systems in 191 countries (Evans et al. 2001). Discussion and critique of this report have stimulated the search for scientific approaches to comparative analysis of national healthcare systems (Radojicic et al. 2020). The study (Varabyova and Müller 2016) analysed 22 papers published on this topic between 1998 and 2014. Twelve of these used DEA and seven used SFA (sometimes in combination with other methods).

The widespread use of the DEA approach for estimating technical efficiency in healthcare can be explained by the following advantages (Cantor and Poh 2017): ability to work with multiple inputs (resources) and outputs (outcomes) simultaneously, without the need to explicitly specify a function representing the relationship between inputs and outputs; ability to compare each unit with similar ones, providing an estimate of relative rather than absolute efficiency; ability to perform calculations without using price information. How-

ever, researchers (Cantor and Poh 2017) also highlighted the following limitations of this approach: sensitivity of results to the choice of input and output variables; inability to explain variation in efficiency estimates; and inoperability where data gaps are present. Some of these limitations can be mitigated through integration with complementary analytical methodologies.

Despite general awareness of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) within the Russian research community, its application in estimating healthcare facility efficiency remains scarce. A search of the eLibrary.ru system using the keywords ‘DEA’, ‘Data Envelopment Analysis’ and ‘Healthcare’ revealed only five studies published in Russian journals and based on Russian data. In (Akindinova et al. 2024), DEA is used to make an international comparison of budget spending efficiency, including healthcare spending. In (Avxentyev et al. 2015) and (Selamzade 2021), a comparative analysis of the efficiency of regional healthcare systems is performed. (Kutyshkin and Shulgin 2023) analysed the efficiency of municipal healthcare facilities in the Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug–Yugra. In (Fedotov et al. 2017), DEA was used to estimate the efficiency of state hospitals in St. Petersburg.

This study uses two-stage DEA to conduct a comparative analysis of the technical efficiency of regional healthcare systems in the Russian Federation. As the practical application of this method requires the selection of input and output indicators, selection of a DEA model and identification of externalities, the first section offers a literature review on the analysis of healthcare system efficiency at national or regional (sub-national) levels, emphasising the above methodological aspects. The second section describes the methodology and information base, and the third section presents and discusses the calculations. The conclusion summarises the main findings.

Literature review

The papers describing the basic DEA models are (Charnes et al. 1978) and (Banker et al. 1984). The method involves constructing an efficient frontier based on a comparison of inputs (resources) and outputs (outcomes). Units that lie on this frontier are considered efficient, while those that do not are considered inefficient. If the ratio of inputs to outputs can change as inputs increase, then it is a model with variable returns to scale; otherwise, it is a model with constant returns to scale. Depending on how the inefficient units reach the efficient frontier, there are three options: input-oriented models (examining how much resource consumption can be reduced while maintaining the current outcome); output-oriented models (examining how much the outcome can be increased while maintaining the same level of resource consumption); and models that allow for variation in both inputs and outputs. (Zhu 2014) offers a good description of the DEA approach.

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses are valuable for selecting a DEA model and the sets of indicators used as inputs, outputs and exogenous (environmental) variables for estimating the efficiency of healthcare facilities. Unlike conventional academic reviews, these summarise the findings of a whole body of research, treating each publication as an object of statistical observation. The resulting database will then be statistically processed, giving the review the characteristics of a rigorous quantitative study.

(Jung et al. 2023) is a systematic review of 123 papers on estimating healthcare efficiency using the DEA approach, published between 2017 and 2022. According to the authors, the Covid-19 pandemic raised the interest in healthcare efficiency. Base DEA models put

forth in (Charnes et al. 1978) and (Banker et al. 1984) are the most widespread ones, but later works are also gaining traction. The most used inputs are bed capacity and head-count, as well as the level of spending. The most used outputs are the number of patients who have received medical care and health indicators such as mortality rate, life expectancy, and patient survival rate. Hospitals are the most common DMUs of analysis, followed by healthcare systems (national or sub-national). Finally, the analysis showed that, despite a broad geography of the studies, the focus was most frequently on healthcare facilities in China.

As for the selection of resources, outcomes, and exogenous variables, (Radojicic et al. 2020) provides a valuable review of 44 research papers that used the DEA method to estimate the efficiency of national healthcare systems. According to the study, the most used inputs are specific healthcare spending, the number of doctors and nurses and bed capacity. The most common outputs are life expectancy, infant survival/mortality rate, under-5 survival/mortality rate, and years of life lost adjusted for disability (Disability Adjusted Life Years, DALYs). The exogenous variables to be most often included are educational levels, GDP, prevalence of tobacco use and obesity, and the proportion of people over 65 years of age.

Varabyova and Müller (2016) conducted a meta-analysis of 22 studies looking at the efficiency of healthcare systems in OECD member countries. The study found that the most common inputs were healthcare spending, healthcare employment and bed capacity, while the most common outputs were life expectancy, mortality rates, healthy life expectancy and years of potential life lost. Exogenous variables included socio-economic factors such as income, unemployment and education; lifestyle factors such as tobacco and alcohol consumption, and support for healthy eating habits; government characteristics; and territorial factors such as OECD membership, tropical climate, and population density. Analysis of the DEA model specification showed that the two most common models were output-oriented model and variable returns to scale model.

Regarding the choice of DEA model, works that provide a substantive justification for the chosen specification are of interest. For example, Dhaoui (2019) and Husseiny (2023) estimated the efficiency of national healthcare systems in the Middle East, North Africa, and Arab countries respectively. They demonstrated that an output-oriented model is more suitable for low- and middle-income countries where resources allocated to healthcare are limited and health indicators are low. Accordingly, achieving the best possible outcomes with the limited resources available should be considered a natural goal in such circumstances. Conversely, an input-oriented model would be more suitable for high-income countries with high healthcare spending and health indicators. In these countries, the more relevant goal is to reduce healthcare costs while maintaining high health indicators. Furthermore, these studies suggest that healthcare facilities do not typically operate at an optimal scale, making variable returns to scale models more appropriate in this area.

The number of studies focusing on the comparative estimation of sub-national healthcare systems is significantly lower compared with national systems. However, such examples can be found in various countries, including Slovakia (Stefko et al. 2018), Saudi Arabia (Abdelfattah and Alanazi 2024) and Taiwan (Wu 2023). In the context of this paper, it makes sense to analyse the Russian data-based studies in more detail.

Avksentyev et al. (2015) used a DEA approach complemented with regression analysis to estimate the efficiency of healthcare systems in Russia's regions (constituent entities). Regrettably, the paper does not offer the DEA model specification. The authors considered

three performance indicators: infant mortality, male and female life expectancy at age one, and one input: per capita allocation according to the Territorial Programme of State Guarantees of Free Provision of Medical Care (TPGG), adjusted for regional differences in the prices of goods and services. The following groups of factors were used as exogenous variables: physical-geographical, demographic, socio-economic, exogenous and behavioural. While most of these factors were significant, the direction of the impact did not always align with the authors’ hypotheses.

Selamzade (2021) conducted a comparative analysis of healthcare efficiency in the 22 constituent entities of the Russian Federation. The input variables were the number of doctors and nurses, and bed capacity per 10,000 population. The output variables were life expectancy at birth, morbidity rate per 1,000 population, and infant mortality rate. The study employed baseline input-oriented DEA models. Three indicators were included as exogenous factors: life expectancy at birth, morbidity per 1.000 population, and the infant mortality rate – the same three factors that were used as outputs in the DEA models. The author provided no explanation for this dual use of the variables.

Data and methods

This study employed a two-stage DEA approach. First, efficiency is estimated using a DEA model. Then, regression analysis is used to identify exogenous factors impacting efficiency levels.

As Russia is considered an average country in terms of health indicators, income levels, and healthcare spending, our study estimated two models: an output-oriented model and an input-oriented model. Both models have variable returns to scale. The results obtained from these models were then compared. We opted for models with variable returns to scale because the regions of the Russian Federation can differ significantly from one another. Using these models allowed to compare each regional system with its most similar ‘analogue’.

From a mathematical perspective, calculation using the DEA method can be seen as solving a constrained extremum problem. The mathematical formalisation of the models used is presented in Table 1. In the formulas presented (1), y_{rj} – r -th output of the j -th DMU, $r = 1 \dots s$; x_{ij} – i -th input of the j -th DMU, $i = 1 \dots m$; s – number of outputs, m – number of inputs, n – number of DMUs.

Table 1. DEA models as constrained extremum problems

Output-oriented model	Input-oriented model
$\varphi^* = \max \varphi$	$\theta^* = \min \theta$
<i>constraints:</i>	<i>constraints:</i>
$\forall r : \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \cdot y_{rj} \geq \varphi \cdot y_{r0}$	$\forall i : \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \cdot x_{ij} \leq \theta \cdot x_{i0}$
$\forall i : \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \cdot x_{ij} \geq x_{i0}$	$\forall r : \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \cdot y_{rj} \geq y_{r0}$
$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j = 1$	$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j = 1$
$\lambda_j \geq 0$	$\lambda_j \geq 0$

Estimating DEA models allowed to:

1) estimate the efficiency of each DMU (φ_j^* and θ_j^* for an output-oriented and input-oriented model, respectively). The DMU is recognised as efficient for both models if the estimate is equal to 1. If $\varphi_j^* > 1$, the DMU is recognised as inefficient for an output-oriented model; if $\theta_j^* < 1$, the DMU is recognised as inefficient for an input-oriented model.

2) for each inefficient DMU, obtain a reference DMU as a linear combination of efficient DMUs. Efficient DMUs included in the reference DMU with non-zero weights (γ_j), are most similar to the inefficient DMU, and their experience may be useful for improving the DMU's efficiency.

3) for each inefficient DMU, estimate the excessive consumption of resources or the failure to achieve the outcomes.

As healthcare systems operate in heterogeneous conditions, DEA model calculation in a two-stage approach was complemented with an exogenous factors analysis using regression. As the calculation may find that multiple DMUs are efficient, a Tobit model, which is designed to work with censored observations, is typically employed. The standard Tobit model is presented in formula (1).

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{y}_j = X' \cdot \beta + \varepsilon_j \\ y_j = \max(\tilde{y}_j, 0) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In the formulas (1) \tilde{y}_j – latent dependent variable, y_j – observable dependent variable, X – factor matrix, β – vector of regression coefficients, ε_j – random error. In the Tobit model, it is assumed that the latent variable is observable in the positive region. If it takes a negative value, the observable variable takes a value of 0.

The input-oriented DEA model gives efficiency scores of 1 for efficient DMUs and less than 1 for inefficient ones. In contrast, the output-oriented DEA model gives efficiency scores of 1 for efficient DMUs and greater than 1 for inefficient ones. In this regard, it is necessary to transform the obtained estimates so that they satisfy condition (1). Transformation (2) was used for the input-oriented DEA model and transformation (3) for the output-oriented DEA model.

$$y_j = \frac{1}{\theta_j^*} - 1, \quad (2)$$

$$y_j = 1 - \frac{1}{\varphi_j^*}. \quad (3)$$

As can be seen from formulas (2) and (3), the indicators y_j obtained based on efficiency estimates and used as a dependent variable in Tobit regressions, take non-negative values. For efficient DMUs, $y_j = 0$. Generally, the lower the efficiency of a DMU, the greater its value. Accordingly, a positive regression coefficient indicates an inverse relationship between a factor and the efficiency of a healthcare system, while a negative coefficient indicates a direct relationship. As the nature of the relationship between the factors and the performance indicator is unknown, a semi-logarithmic model, in which the quantitative factors were pre-logarithmised, was also evaluated alongside the linear model.

The calculations were performed in R. The DEA models were estimated using functions from the *deaR* package and the Tobit models, using the *AER* package.

Selecting input, output and exogenous indicators is challenging. Our work started with reviewing the literature on estimating the efficiency of national and regional (sub-national) healthcare systems, after which we looked at the regional-level data available, and finally examined specific health characteristics of the Russian population. The resource indicators (inputs) included in the analysis are the number of doctors and nursing staff as workforce indicators; bed capacity as an indicator of fixed asset size; and the level of regional healthcare system funding coming from two sources: budgets at all levels and regional compulsory medical insurance funds. The performance indicators used were life expectancy and infant survival rate, which are practically the de facto standard in studies on healthcare efficiency. Next, two more indicators were added: survival rates for men and women of working age. We deemed that including these indicators was reasonable for the following reasons. Firstly, a significant (more than 10-year) gap in life expectancy between men and women is a distinctive feature of the Russian demographics. Secondly, it is the loss of the working-age population that causes the greatest socio-economic damage. Thirdly, the loss of the working-age population is largely preventable, including through timely, high-quality medical care.

The following exogenous factors, which could impact healthcare efficiency, were considered:

Firstly, socio-economic indicators, such as GDP per capita, poverty level and the proportion of population with higher education.

Secondly, demographic indicators, including the proportions of the population living in urban areas versus villages or small towns, and the proportion of population over 65 years of age.

Thirdly, lifestyle indicators, such as smoking prevalence, alcohol consumption and mortality from external causes. These correspond to the main groups of exogenous characteristics that the healthcare system takes into account. In addition to the above, one more indicator describing the region's climatic conditions was included in the analysis. This indicator was based on the region's climate zone. According to this classification, the regions of the Russian Federation are divided into five climate zones. Zones 4 and 5 (special) are the regions with the most adverse climatic conditions. This indicator was included due to the significant differences in natural and climatic conditions across the regions of the Russian Federation, and because a number of studies have linked variations in population health indicators to the impact of natural and climatic conditions. For example, a study analysing population mortality and associated human capital losses concluded that high positions in the ranking (i.e. positions with minimal losses) were due to either high socio-economic development (regions such as Moscow, St. Petersburg, Belgorod Oblast, Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug, and Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug–Yugra) or favourable natural and climatic conditions (regions such as the North Caucasus and Stavropol Krai) (Reiting regionov... 2024).

The study's information base was formed using statistical books 'Regions of Russia' (https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/Region_Pokaz_2023.rar), 'Healthcare in Russia' (appendix to the book: information broken down by constituent entities of the Russian Federation https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/Pril_Zdravooxran_2023.rar), results of the 2020 All-Russian Population Census (<https://rosstat.gov.ru/vpn/2020>), as well as data retrieved from the Unified Interdepartmental Information and Statistical System (UIISS). The data array included indicators for 85 Russian regions for 2022. The only exceptions were smoking prevalence, which was taken from the UIISS (only data for 2023 is available), and indicators retrieved from the 2020 census results. Cost indicators

were adjusted for regional differences in price by dividing them by the cost of a fixed basket of consumer goods and services. Appendix 1 presents the indicators of resources (inputs), outcomes and the environment used in the calculations, as well as their sources and the methods used to obtain them. Table 2 presents descriptive statistics. As many researchers have noted the unreliability of statistical data for the North Caucasus regions, the study includes calculations based on both the full list of regions and a list excluding the North Caucasus regions.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

No.	Indicator	Min	Q1	Me	Q3	Max	M	SD
1	Specific healthcare spending	0.89	1.25	1.37	1.64	5.65	1.66	0.82
2	Number of doctors per 10,000 population	30.90	43.10	48.20	54.50	89.10	49.49	10.23
3	Bed capacity per 10,000 population	43.50	75.20	81.90	92.70	135.20	83.28	15.13
4	Number of nursing and midwifery staff per 10,000 population	66.40	95.30	104.00	113.80	165.20	105.89	18.44
5	Life expectancy at birth	66.20	70.35	71.56	73.03	78.34	71.78	2.36
6	Infant survival rate	984.2	994.6	995.6	996.1	996.9	995.2	1.60
7	Working-age male survival rate	986.7	989.6	990.6	992.2	997.4	991.0	2.06
8	Working-age female survival rate	994.5	997.1	997.5	997.9	999.3	997.5	0.74
9	GDP per capita	10.04	24.10	33.62	44.43	417.52	47.87	59.84
10	Population with monetary income below the poverty line	4.50	9.00	11.50	14.20	30.50	12.14	4.65
11	Percentage of population with higher education	17.57	24.37	26.26	29.17	43.19	27.26	4.64
12	Proportion of urban population	30.80	64.20	71.40	78.30	100.00	70.90	12.95
13	Percentage of population living in cities with a population over 50,000	0.00	44.19	56.16	67.67	100.00	56.53	17.53
14	Population above working age	9.70	22.30	24.50	27.00	30.10	23.82	4.54
15	Population density	0.07	4.55	23.76	43.67	5040.08	142.05	692.09
16	Prevalence of tobacco smoking among people aged 15 years and over	1.20	17.20	20.50	22.60	39.90	20.17	6.12
17	Mortality from external causes per 100,000 population	29.31	91.05	111.56	129.29	231.33	112.90	37.10
18	Alcohol consumption	0.22	15.42	18.64	23.95	36.60	19.11	7.66

Findings and Discussion

Table 4 and Figure 1 show estimates of the efficiency of regional healthcare systems.

As can be seen in Table 4, 18 regions are rated as efficient when calculations are based on the full list, and this set is the same for both DEA models: city of Sevastopol, Republic of Ingushetia, Leningrad Oblast, Kurgan Oblast, Republic of Dagestan, Lipetsk Oblast, Volgda Oblast, Republic of Tatarstan, Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug–Yugra, city of Moscow, Kabardino-Balkarian Republic, Chechen Republic, Udmurt Republic, Chuvash Republic, Saratov Oblast, Kaluga Oblast, Republic of Adygea, Stavropol Krai. Nevertheless, their position in the ranking depends largely on the chosen model. For instance, Magadan Oblast is ranked 9th in terms of efficiency using an output-oriented model but falls to 62nd using an input-oriented model. The Chukotka Autonomous Okrug healthcare system demonstrates the lowest level of efficiency in both models.

Figure 1. Map of Russian regions by healthcare efficiency (Output-oriented model, all regions)

Excluding the regions of the North Caucasus, 15 regions proved to be efficient in both models. Fourteen of them are included in the list of the 18 that are efficient in calculations based on the full list of regions, and one, the Republic of Kalmykia, which ranked high (7th and 11th in the output-oriented and input-oriented models, respectively), was added to the list of efficient regions. Maintaining efficiency while reducing the size of the population is a well-known feature of the DEA method. At the same time, four regions of the North Caucasus lie on the efficient frontier (Republic of Ingushetia, Republic of Dagestan, Kabardino-Balkarian Republic, Chechen Republic), and their removal causes the efficient frontier to be ‘locally redrawn,’ giving inefficient regions a chance to become efficient.

Table 5 shows the identification of reference DMUs for the five least and five most inefficient DMUs according to the output-oriented model.

As shown in Table 5, the choice of model substantially affects the identification of the reference DMU. A comparison of results for the full list of regions with those obtained after excluding the North Caucasus reveals that the reference DMU remains unchanged after the regions in question were excluded (such is the case of Moscow Oblast and the city of St Petersburg). Otherwise, the reference DMU is reconfigured.

The Tobit model estimates are reported in Tables 6 and 7.

Table 4. Efficiency estimates of regional healthcare systems

Region	Output-oriented model				Input-oriented model			
	All regions		Excluding North Caucasus		All regions		Excluding North Caucasus	
	ϕ_j^*	Rank	ϕ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank
Sevastopol, city of	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Republic of Ingushetia	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-
Leningrad Oblast	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Kurgan Oblast	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Republic of Dagestan	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-
Lipetsk Oblast	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Vologda Oblast	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Republic of Tatarstan	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Khanty–Mansi Autonomous Okrug–Yugra	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Moscow, city of	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Kabardino–Balkarian Republic	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-
Chechen Republic	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-
Udmurt Republic	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Chuvash Republic	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Saratov Oblast	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Kaluga Oblast	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Republic of Adygea	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Stavropol Krai	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Moscow Oblast	1.00001	2	1.00001	2	0.99390	2	0.99390	2
Republic of North Ossetia–Alania	1.00010	3	-	-	0.86636	21	-	-
St. Petersburg, city of	1.00015	4	1.00015	4	0.80666	37	0.80666	40
Yamalo–Nenets Autonomous Okrug	1.00018	5	1.00015	5	0.71959	55	0.73383	53

Region	Output-oriented model				Input-oriented model			
	All regions		Excluding North Caucasus		All regions		Excluding North Caucasus	
	φ_j^*	Rank	φ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank
Tyumen Oblast	1.00020	6	1.00049	18	0.79619	39	0.75238	49
Republic of Kalmykia	1.00026	7	1	1	0.91473	11	1	1
Karachay-Cherkess Republic	1.00027	8	-	-	0.97049	4	-	-
Magadan Oblast	1.00030	9	1.00030	7	0.64206	62	0.64206	61
Voronezh Oblast	1.00033	10	1.00032	8	0.81922	35	0.81936	35
Krasnodar Krai	1.00036	11	1.00034	9	0.94209	7	0.94512	7
Republic of Mordovia	1.00038	12	1.00023	6	0.89022	15	0.89832	14
Belgorod Oblast	1.00039	13	1.00014	3	0.85741	25	0.91296	11
Mari El Republic	1.00039	14	1.00036	11	0.96599	5	0.98026	5
Yaroslavl Oblast	1.00042	15	1.00042	15	0.84572	29	0.84633	27
Rostov Oblast	1.00051	16	1.00040	12	0.98049	3	0.99120	4
Republic of Sakha (Yakutia)	1.00055	17	1.00044	16	0.62499	64	0.66615	58
Volgograd Oblast	1.00055	18	1.00035	10	0.88975	16	0.89367	16
Vladimir Oblast	1.00057	19	1.00057	21	0.94163	8	0.94518	6
Tomsk Oblast	1.00059	20	1.00059	22	0.73302	52	0.73334	54
Nenets Autonomous Okrug	1.00059	21	1.00042	13	0.70738	57	0.75691	47
Ulyanovsk Oblast	1.00061	22	1.00060	23	0.92157	10	0.92264	10
Kostroma Oblast	1.00062	23	1.00062	26	0.90142	12	0.90325	13
Smolensk Oblast	1.00065	24	1.00061	24	0.93655	9	0.94063	8
Republic of Bashkortostan	1.00070	25	1.00062	25	0.84880	28	0.84880	26
Murmansk Oblast	1.00070	26	1.00070	29	0.64891	61	0.64891	60
Chelyabinsk Oblast	1.00072	27	1.00071	31	0.86995	19	0.87258	22
Orenburg Oblast	1.00074	28	1.00074	32	0.83214	31	0.83566	31

Region	Output-oriented model				Input-oriented model			
	All regions		Excluding North Caucasus		All regions		Excluding North Caucasus	
	φ_j^*	Rank	φ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank
Altai Krai	1.00077	29	1.00077	33	0.85403	27	0.85403	25
Penza Oblast	1.00078	30	1.00064	27	0.83568	30	0.83914	30
Kursk Oblast	1.00084	31	1.00052	19	0.74814	49	0.78132	44
Novgorod Oblast	1.00084	32	1.00083	36	0.85648	26	0.85736	24
Republic of Komi	1.00090	33	1.00090	40	0.65372	60	0.65372	59
Kaliningrad Oblast	1.00093	34	1.00046	17	0.89265	14	0.89366	17
Tula Oblast	1.00104	35	1.00101	44	0.86918	20	0.88982	19
Bryansk Oblast	1.00105	36	1.00082	35	0.87982	17	0.93760	9
Tambov Oblast	1.00108	37	1.00069	28	0.85897	23	0.90350	12
Nizhny Novgorod Oblast	1.00108	38	1.00088	39	0.83210	32	0.84575	28
Astrakhan Oblast	1.00109	39	1.00042	14	0.77206	45	0.82995	32
Republic of Tyva	1.00109	40	1.00109	48	0.68354	59	0.68589	56
Arkhangelsk Oblast	1.00111	41	1.00113	49	0.61117	65	0.63350	62
Pskov Oblast	1.00113	42	1.00088	38	0.94761	6	0.99351	3
Kirov Oblast	1.00114	43	1.00083	37	0.73378	51	0.75667	48
Omsk Oblast	1.00115	44	1.00091	41	0.77540	44	0.81255	38
Sverdlovsk Oblast	1.00116	45	1.00096	43	0.78679	42	0.80263	42
Republic of Buryatia	1.00121	46	1.00120	53	0.81166	36	0.82053	34
Sakhalin Oblast	1.00122	47	1.00118	50	0.50447	67	0.50550	64
Perm Krai	1.00122	48	1.00107	47	0.78805	41	0.80858	39
Samara Oblast	1.00125	49	1.00107	46	0.86414	22	0.88390	20
Amur Oblast	1.00125	50	1.00125	55	0.70582	58	0.70999	55
Republic of Khakassia	1.00125	51	1.00106	45	0.87265	18	0.88987	18

Region	Output-oriented model				Input-oriented model			
	All regions		Excluding North Caucasus		All regions		Excluding North Caucasus	
	φ_j^*	Rank	φ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank	θ_j^*	Rank
Republic of Crimea	1.00128	52	1.00071	30	0.79388	40	0.81884	36
Ryazan Oblast	1.00137	53	1.00053	20	0.76887	46	0.84432	29
Novosibirsk Oblast	1.00139	54	1.00093	42	0.77994	43	0.79947	43
Krasnoyarsk Krai	1.00146	55	1.00120	52	0.71330	56	0.75190	50
Khabarovsk Krai	1.00153	56	1.00147	58	0.76565	47	0.76762	46
Irkutsk Oblast	1.00162	57	1.00162	59	0.73073	53	0.74817	51
Jewish Autonomous Oblast	1.00172	58	1.00172	61	0.89739	13	0.89739	15
Ivanovo Oblast	1.00173	59	1.00121	54	0.82967	33	0.88281	21
Oryol Oblast	1.00180	60	1.00080	34	0.75666	48	0.80330	41
Primorsky Krai	1.00190	61	1.00128	56	0.85793	24	0.85793	23
Republic of Karelia	1.00191	62	1.00191	64	0.63766	63	0.68440	57
Zabaykalsky Krai	1.00193	63	1.00178	62	0.72354	54	0.74779	52
Kamchatka Krai	1.00201	64	1.00146	57	0.58437	66	0.58463	63
Kemerovo Oblast	1.00207	65	1.00185	63	0.79884	38	0.81354	37
Tver Oblast	1.00220	66	1.00170	60	0.82188	34	0.82718	33
Altai Republic	1.00221	67	1.00120	51	0.74678	50	0.77543	45
Chukotka Autonomous Okrug	1.00483	68	1.00392	65	0.44641	68	0.44642	65
<i>Minimum</i>	1.00001		1.00001		0.44641		0.44642	
<i>Lower quartile</i>	1.00056		1.00046		0.73340		0.75238	
<i>Median</i>	1.00104		1.00077		0.81922		0.82718	
<i>Upper quartile</i>	1.00127		1.00113		0.87130		0.89366	
<i>Maximum</i>	1.00483		1.00392		0.99390		0.99390	

Table 5. Identifying a reference for inefficient DMUs

Region	Output-oriented model, λ_i		Input-oriented model, λ_i	
	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus
Moscow Oblast	Kaluga Oblast (0.08506)	Kaluga Oblast (0.08506)	Kaluga Oblast (0.07360)	Kaluga Oblast (0.07360)
	Moscow, city of (0.17894)	Moscow, city of (0.17894)	Moscow, city of (0.17523)	Moscow, city of (0.17523)
	Leningrad Oblast (0.57161)	Leningrad Oblast (0.57161)	Leningrad Oblast (0.59650)	Leningrad Oblast (0.59650)
	Sevastopol, city of (0.13150)	Sevastopol, city of (0.13150)	Sevastopol, city of (0.12469)	Sevastopol, city of (0.12469)
	Republic of Tatarstan (0.03288)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.03288)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.02999)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.02999)
Republic of North Ossetia-Alania	Republic of Ingushetia (0.00015)	-	Sevastopol, city of (0.21773)	-
	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.99985)	-	Republic of Ingushetia (0.08878)	-
	-	-	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.66598)	-
	-	-	Stavropol Krai (0.02750)	-
	-	-	Kaluga Oblast (0.03153)	Kaluga Oblast (0.03153)
St. Petersburg, city of	Moscow, city of (0.50731)	Moscow, city of (0.50731)	Moscow, city of (0.58297)	Moscow, city of (0.58297)
	Republic of Tatarstan (0.20766)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.20766)	Sevastopol, city of (0.19800)	Sevastopol, city of (0.19800)
	Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug (0.28503)	Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug-Yugra (0.28503)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.18749)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.18749)
	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.15408)	Moscow, city of (0.50064)	Moscow, city of (0.26170)	Moscow, city of (0.25316)
Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug	Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug (0.84592)	Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug-Yugra (0.49936)	Leningrad Oblast (0.20386)	Leningrad Oblast (0.10126)
	-	-	Republic of Ingushetia (0.04508)	Sevastopol, city of (0.27215)
			Republic of Tatarstan (0.48936)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.37342)

Region	Output-oriented model, λ_i		Input-oriented model, λ_j	
	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus
Tyumen Oblast	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.12305)	Moscow, city of (0.35675)	Leningrad Oblast (0.19916)	Moscow, city of (0.14286)
	Republic of Tatarstan (0.59644)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.41910)	Sevastopol, city of (0.01534)	Leningrad Oblast (0.85714)
	Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug (0.28051)	Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug (0.22415)	Republic of Ingushetia (0.07786)	
	Republic of Ingushetia (0.21392)	Moscow, city of (0.54545)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.70763)	
Kamchatka Krai	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.78608)	Stavropol Krai (0.45455)	Leningrad Oblast (0.58483)	Leningrad Oblast (0.81681)
	Leningrad Oblast (0.11754)	Republic of Adygea (0.34975)	Chechen Republic (0.41517)	Kurgan Oblast (0.18319)
Kemerovo Oblast	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.51414)	Republic of Kalmykia (0.46594)	Leningrad Oblast (0.48618)	Leningrad Oblast (0.54389)
	Chechen Republic (0.02086)	Republic of Tatarstan (0.18430)	Chechen Republic (0.51382)	Republic of Adygea (0.29044)
	Republic of Tatarstan (0.34746)	Republic of Adygea (0.17682)	Kurgan Oblast (0.16567)	
Tver Oblast	Moscow, city of (0.11183)	Moscow, city of (0.17682)	Leningrad Oblast (0.21432)	Leningrad Oblast (0.11044)
	Sevastopol, city of (0.10495)	Republic of Adygea (0.19857)	Sevastopol, city of (0.47672)	Republic of Adygea (0.51611)
	Republic of Ingushetia (0.20590)	Stavropol Krai (0.62462)	Chechen Republic (0.30896)	Sevastopol, city of (0.37344)
	Kabardino-Balkarian Republic (0.57732)	Stavropol Krai (0.80530)		
Altai Republic	Republic of Ingushetia (1)	Moscow, city of (0.07860)	Republic of Ingushetia (0.09055)	Leningrad Oblast (0.76325)
		Republic of Adygea (0.11609)	Chechen Republic (0.90945)	Republic of Adygea (0.22332)
		Stavropol Krai (0.80530)		Kurgan Oblast (0.01343)
Chukotka Autonomous Okrug	Republic of Ingushetia (1)	Moscow, city of (1)	Leningrad Oblast (0.98073)	Leningrad Oblast (0.9915)
			Chechen Republic (0.01927)	Kurgan Oblast (0.0085)

Table 6. Results of regression analysis, linear specification

Factor	Output-oriented model		Input-oriented model	
	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus
Constant	-0.001179 (0.001556)	0.000249 (0.002039)	-0.444200 (0.438000)	-0.121200 (0.486300)
Climate zone				
1–2 (base)				
3	-0.000015 (0.000249)	-0.000063 (0.000256)	0.117200* (0.063840)	0.095990 (0.060720)
4–5	-0.000031 (0.000403)	-0.000100 (0.000412)	0.360700*** (0.102800)	0.328500*** (0.097160)
GDP per capita	-0.000003* (0.000002)	-0.000003* (0.000002)	-0.000518 (0.000452)	-0.000655 (0.000429)
Population with incomes below the poverty line	-0.000012 (0.000029)	-0.000018 (0.000031)	-0.008746 (0.007550)	-0.015610* (0.007490)
Percentage of population with higher education	0.000077 (0.002886)	-0.002421 (0.003546)	0.974200 (0.788700)	0.141500 (0.852200)
Proportion of urban population	0.000002 (0.000014)	0.000003 (0.000014)	-0.000102 (0.003519)	-0.001254 (0.003393)
Percentage of population living in large cities	-0.000002 (0.000009)	-0.000003 (0.000009)	-0.001668 (0.002241)	-0.000060 (0.002244)
Population above working age	-0.000007 (0.000031)	-0.000033 (0.000040)	0.002572 (0.008795)	-0.003379 (0.009549)

Factor	Output-oriented model		Input-oriented model	
	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus
Population density	0.000000 (0.000000)	0.000000 (0.000000)	-0.000009 (0.000041)	0.000012 (0.000040)
Prevalence of tobacco smoking among people aged 15 years and over	0.000053*** (0.000020)	0.000048** (0.000021)	0.003924 (0.005303)	0.004013 (0.005119)
Alcohol consumption	0.000013 (0.000019)	0.000017 (0.000020)	0.002263 (0.004836)	0.006043 (0.004788)
Mortality from external causes per 100,000 population	0.000009*** (0.000003)	0.000008** (0.000004)	0.002962*** (0.000870)	0.003222*** (0.000889)
Likelihood logarithm	379.8	368.1	8.163	11.83
Wald statistic	58.43	47.35	90.1	97.49
P	<<0.001	<<0.001	<<0.001	<<0.001
N	85	79	85	79
Number of left-censored observations	18	15	18	15
Number of uncensored observations	67	64	67	64

Note: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 7. Results of regression analysis, semi-logarithmic specification

Factor	Output-oriented model		Input-oriented model	
	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus
Constant	-0.003756 (0.003764)	-0.006379** (0.003158)	-1.744330* (0.969120)	-2.039790** (0.977540)
Climate zone				
1–2 (base)				
3	-0.000148 (0.000257)	-0.000023 (0.000205)	0.066850 (0.063150)	0.057000 (0.062740)
4–5	-0.000732 (0.000489)	-0.000524 (0.000379)	0.171120 (0.119930)	0.168590 (0.116020)
GDP per capita	-0.000103 (0.000261)	-0.000028 (0.000204)	0.106110 (0.064800)	0.109660* (0.063050)
Population with incomes below the poverty line	-0.000028 (0.000396)	-0.000059 (0.000309)	-0.024270 (0.096810)	-0.056380 (0.094150)
Percentage of population with higher education	-0.000001 (0.000779)	-0.000934 (0.000693)	0.378020* (0.203160)	0.197580 (0.209320)
Proportion of urban population	0.000755 (0.000776)	0.001015 (0.000632)	0.180600 (0.192800)	0.100910 (0.194060)
Percentage of population living in large cities	-0.000599 (0.000455)	-0.000431 (0.000388)	-0.206380* (0.112950)	-0.148730 (0.119600)
Population above working age	-0.000370 (0.000706)	-0.000800 (0.000586)	0.209240 (0.184390)	0.074740 (0.179250)

Factor	Output-oriented model		Input-oriented model	
	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus	All regions	Excluding North Caucasus
Population density	-0.000192* (0.000104)	-0.000103 (0.000081)	-0.041450 (0.025260)	-0.024400 (0.024450)
Prevalence of tobacco smoking among people aged 15 years and over	0.000764** (0.000382)	0.000572* (0.000298)	0.065160 (0.095060)	0.074080 (0.091970)
Alcohol consumption	0.000247 (0.000295)	0.000412 (0.000288)	-0.072070 (0.072960)	0.039160 (0.088130)
Mortality from external causes per 100,000 population	0.000634 (0.000481)	0.000720* (0.000393)	0.339840*** (0.123250)	0.389770*** (0.121540)
Likelihood logarithm	375.9	375.7	12.73	14.76
Wald statistic	59.47	75.43	103.7	110.4
P	<<0.001	<<0.001	<<0.001	<<0.001
N	84	78	84	78
Number of left-censored observations	18	15	18	15
Number of uncensored observations	66	63	66	63

Note: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$; The reduction in the number of observations by 1 in the semi-logarithmic specification is due to the presence of a zero value in the factor variable.

As shown in Tables 6 and 7, lifestyle factors proved to be the most ‘responsive’ – in almost all models, a higher mortality from external causes is accompanied by a greater healthcare system inefficiency. When efficiency estimates are calculated using an output-oriented model, smoking prevalence emerges as a significant factor: the higher the percentage of the population that smoke, the less efficient the healthcare system is. Demographic and economic factors are often insignificant. Natural and climatic conditions are significant in calculations based on efficiency estimates obtained using an input-oriented model with a linear specification. If a region is climate zone 4 – an area with very low temperatures, situated in the Arctic zone, including the northern edges of the Eurasian continent, lands and islands in the Arctic Ocean; or climate zone 5 – which is defined as the special climate belt located not far from the Arctic zone, in the Far North, and is characterised by a harsh climate and the coldest temperatures, then the efficiency of the regional healthcare system decreases compared to the regions of climate zone 1 (subtropical climate) and climate zone 2 (temperate continental climate).

Studies based on the two-stage DEA approach often reveal the insignificance of many factors that are conventionally considered to have an impact on public health and healthcare. One possible explanation for this is that the calculations are based on a small number of observations, meaning only strong effects can be verified. Table 8 provides a comparative analysis of three studies estimating the technical efficiency of national healthcare systems, followed by multifactor analysis.

Table 8. Results of the analysis of factors affecting the efficiency of national health systems

Group of factors	Study		
	(Afonso and Aubyn 2011) 44 countries classified as developed countries	(Pérez-Cárceles et al. 2017) 49 European and Central Asian countries	(Radojicic et al. 2020) 38 OECD or BRICS member countries
Socio-economic	GDP per capita (+)	GDP per capita (-)	GDP per capita (-)
	GDP growth rate (+)	School enrolment (-)	Percentage of population with higher education (-)
	Level of education (+)		
Demographic		Percentage of population aged 65 and over (±)	
		Population density (-)	
Lifestyle	Prevalence of obesity (+)	Prevalence of obesity (-)	Prevalence of obesity (+)
	Tobacco use (+)	Tobacco use (+)	Tobacco use (-)
Other		Vaccination coverage (±)	Features of healthcare system funding (-)
		Region (±)	

Note: (+) significant factor; (-) insignificant factor; (±) the study evaluated several models; sometimes the factor was significant and sometimes it was not.

As shown in Table 8, socio-economic and demographic factors are not consistently identified as significant in other studies that use similar instruments. Lifestyle factors are more frequently found to have a significant effect on healthcare efficiency than factors in other groups.

The proven impact of lifestyle factors on the efficiency of regional healthcare systems highlights the importance of fostering a culture of self-preservation in society. This includes not only health-protective behaviours such as abstaining from alcohol, tobacco and drugs, but also managing risk-taking and conflict-aggravating behaviours and complying with traffic and safety regulations.

Importantly, as with virtually any empirical study, this one has certain limitations that require caution when interpreting the results. Firstly, the study was based on data from a single year. Conducting the analysis over a longer time interval would have made it possible to assess the robustness of the efficiency estimates and the reliability of the findings obtained from the factor analysis. Secondly, input and output indicators were primarily selected based on similar studies and data availability. However, the author cannot be certain that the 'optimal set' has been used. For instance, this study, like many others, considers life expectancy as an outcome, while it is known to be affected not only by the healthcare system, but also by many other factors. In addition, the study considers spending from budgets and territorial compulsory medical insurance funds (TFOMS) as resources, but not the population's spending on medical services. Including this spending in the analysis would enable a more accurate evaluation of financial resources available in the healthcare sector. A similar issue arises with other resource indicators, such as numbers of doctors, nursing and midwifery staff, and bed capacity: the study considers the resources of state or municipal healthcare facilities, but not those of corporate or private healthcare facilities. Furthermore, the author believes that it would be beneficial to include indicators of regional healthcare systems' high-tech equipment availability. This aspect was not covered in this study due to a lack of data. Overall, developing an optimal set of indicators for the comparative analysis of regional healthcare systems in the Russian Federation is a complex, interdisciplinary, conceptual task requiring the collective efforts of the research community.

Conclusion

Efficient management of healthcare resources is a relevant issue for Russia and many other countries. One modern approach to estimating the efficiency of healthcare facilities is Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). This method has several attractive features, including a sound theoretical basis, its ability to work with multiple inputs and outputs, and its being data-oriented, so that calculations are performed solely on the basis of data, without the need for additional information such as weights. It also produces reference decision-making units (DMUs) whose experience can be used to improve the efficiency of inefficient DMUs, as well as quantitative estimates of input and output slacks.

This study used a two-stage DEA to estimate the technical efficiency of regional (sub-national) healthcare systems in the Russian Federation. A review of the literature – primarily systematic reviews and meta-analyses on the application of DEA to estimating the efficiency of healthcare facilities – provided guidance on selecting inputs, outputs, and exogenous factors. However, the final set was also expanded by adding Russia's specific characteristics.

Calculations based on two DEA models identified 18 efficient regions in Russia. Analysis of regional inefficiency ratings showed that the ranking depends significantly on the chosen model. Therefore, justifying the model specification is essential for the practical application of the method. In the author's opinion, this issue has not yet been studied sufficiently.

The analysis of the impact of exogenous factors on the efficiency of regional healthcare systems demonstrated that lifestyle factors significantly impact efficiency. Factors in other groups were more often insignificant.

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Appendix

Table A1. Variables used in the analysis

No.	Description	Source or method of construction	Unit of measurement	Used As
1	Specific healthcare spending	Constructed. (Consolidated budget spending on healthcare + TFOMS spending/average annual cost of a fixed basket of consumer goods and services/Average annual population. Spending data: 'Healthcare in Russia'; Average annual population: 'Regions of Russia'. Average annual cost of a fixed basket of consumer goods and services: UIISS, https://www.fedstat.ru/indicator/31052	times/person	Resource
2	Number of doctors per 10,000 population	'Regions of Russia'	doctors/ 10,000 population	Resource
3	Bed capacity per 10,000 population	'Regions of Russia'	hospital beds/ 10,000 population	Resource
4	Number of nursing and midwifery staff per 10,000 population	'Regions of Russia'	Nursing & midwifery staff/10,000 population	Resource
5	Life expectancy at birth	'Regions of Russia'	Years	Output
6	Infant survival rate	Constructed. Infant mortality rate per 1,000 live births. Infant mortality rates are derived from the book 'Regions of Russia.'	children/ per 1,000 live births	Output
7	Working-age male survival rate	Constructed. 1000 – working-age male mortality (per 1,000) 'Regions of Russia'	men/1,000 men	Output

No.	Description	Source or method of construction	Unit of measurement	Used As
8	Working-age female survival rate	Constructed. 1000 – working-age female mortality (per 1.000) 'Regions of Russia'	women/1.000 women	Output
9	GRP per capita (GRP)	Constructed. GRP per capita/(Average annual cost of a fixed basket of consumer goods and services*12) GRP per capita: 'Regions of Russia' Average annual cost of a fixed basket of consumer goods and services – UIISS, https://www.fedstat.ru/indikator/31052	times/person	Exogenous factor
10	Percentage of population with higher education	Constructed. All-Russian Population Census 2020, Volume 3, Table 1	%	Exogenous factor
11	Population with monetary income below the poverty line (Poverty)	'Regions of Russia'	%	Exogenous factor
12	Proportion of urban population	'Regions of Russia'	%	Exogenous factor
13	Proportion of population living in large cities	Constructed. Proportion of urban population*(1 – Proportion of population of small towns (<50.000) in the total urban population) Proportion of urban population: 'Regions of Russia' Proportion of population of small towns (<50.000) in the total urban population: All-Russian Population Census 2020, Volume 1, Table 6.	%	Exogenous factor
14	Population density	Constructed. Population /Area Population and Area: 'Regions of Russia' (Table 1.1)	persons per km ²	Exogenous factor

No.	Description	Source or method of construction	Unit of measurement	Used As
15	Population above working age	'Regions of Russia'	%	Exogenous factor
16	Prevalence of tobacco smoking among people aged 15 years and over	UIISS, https://fedstat.ru/indicator/62581	%	Exogenous factor
17	Mortality from external causes per 100,000 population	UIISS, https://fedstat.ru/indicator/31270	deaths per 100,000 population	Exogenous factor
18	Alcohol consumption	Constructed. Physical retail sales of alcoholic beverages/ (Average annual population* (1 – Proportion of population younger than working age)); Physical retail sales of alcoholic beverages: UIISS, https://fedstat.ru/indicator/57959 Average annual population (Table 1.2) and Proportion of population younger than working age (Table 2.5): 'Regions of Russia'	litres per capita	Exogenous factor
19	Climatic conditions	Distribution of regions by climate zones. R 2.2.2006-05. 2.2. Occupational health. Guidelines for the hygienic assessment of factors in the working environment and work processes. Criteria and classification of working conditions (Approved by the Chief State Sanitary Physician of the Russian Federation on 29 July 2005) Appendix 13. Climate zones (belts) of Russia. According to this document, the regions of the Russian Federation are divided into five categories based primarily on average annual temperature and wind speed: IV (I) (-1.0 °C, 2.7 m/s): referred to as 'first' in the paper; III (II) (-9.7 °C, 5.6 m/s): referred to as 'second' in the paper; II (III) (-18.0 °C, 3.6 m/s): referred to as 'third' in the paper; Ib (IV) (-41 °C, 1.3 m/s): referred to as 'fourth' in the paper; Ia ('special') (-25 °C, 6.8 m/s): referred to as 'fifth' in the paper.	–	Exogenous factor